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Outcomes of an online practice exam utilising Confidence Based Marking

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INTRODUCTION

Since their inception over 100 years ago (Goodenough, 1950), tests and exams constructed using Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) have been widely used as a form of assessment in higher education due to their high level of reliability, versatility, efficiency and ease of marking (Roediger III & Marsh, 2005). Despite the wide usage of MCQs and detailed published guidelines for their construction (Haladyna, Downing, & Rodriguez, 2002), there remain inherent limitations such as the difficulty of detecting the guessing of answers (Burton, 2001), the inability to test higher-level cognitive functions and the lack of opportunity for a student to show the working used to obtain the selected answer in order to obtain partial credit (McAllister & Guidice, 2012).

The basic, most common form of MCQ, the “one correct option” style, has been adapted over the years to spawn a range of types that attempt to address the inherent limitations in such a scheme (Rowley & Traub, 1977; Albanese & Sabers, 1988). Alternative grading schemes have been utilised such as allowing more than one correct answer, weighting answers according to their quality and negative marking for incorrect answers (Siddiqui, Bhavsar, Bhavsar, & Bose, 2016). Despite these measures there is still a perceived unfairness in MCQs (McCoubrie, 2004), where students can still obtain a correct answer through an amount of guessing and process of elimination, rather than through the intended cognitive process being tested.

An alternative method to combat some of the aforementioned shortcomings in the use of MCQs is to require an extra metric to be provided with the response to each question indicating the confidence that the student has in their selected answer. Confidence-

Based Marking (CBM), in which a student must indicate their confidence level in each answer and be graded according to a suitably designed marking scheme, helps to encourage reflection, justification and rigour (Gardner-Medwin, 1995). It rewards both justification to the point of high confidence and the ability to identify reasons for reservation about an answer, and therefore encourages a more rigorous approach both to learning and assessment (Bryan & Clegg, 2006). Students' misconceptions are highlighted when they receive the feedback and the system is perceived as more realistic and fair in that it eliminates a large amount of guessing.

This paper describes the implementation of a CBM MCQ test in a first-year engineering subject through an online practice exam, held in the final week of semester. Feedback was provided to students on their accuracy, measured as the number of correctly answered questions, and the reliability of their assessment of their knowledge, through a CBM-weighted mark and calculated bonus. The goal of the practice exam was to identify individuals' strengths and weaknesses in the subject material in order to guide their study in the Study Without Teaching Vacation (SWOT Vac) period and during the exam period. Data was collected on the performance and confidence levels for each student for each question and analysed to identify relationships and differences across sub groups of students.

1 CONFIDENCE BASED MARKING

To alleviate some of the inherent shortcomings of MCQs and increase the quality of the feedback provided to the students heading into the exam study period, the online practice exam implemented CBM. When using CBM with MCQs, students are asked to state with each answer their level of confidence, C , in the correctness of their decision – $C = 1$ (Low), 2 (Medium), or 3 (High). If the answer is correct, then this is the score awarded. An incorrect answer leads to a score of zero for level 1, and -2 or -6 for levels 2 and 3 respectively. Level 2 gives equally weighted negative marking for wrong answers. Students are told to choose level 2 unless they are very confident (>80% chance of being right), when they should choose level 3, or rather hesitant (<67% chance of being correct), when level 1 is appropriate. This strategy is optimal to maximise their expected scores. The expected average CBM mark for a given percentage correct, or accuracy level, for the three confidence levels is given in *Figure 1*. A student can never expect to gain systematically by either overestimating or underestimating confidence. High marks are obtained firstly, of course, by getting the answer correct.

A bonus is added to the simple accuracy as a measure of how well the student categorises responses as uncertain or reliable (Bryan & Clegg, 2006). The bonus is positive or negative, proportional to the amount the average CBM mark is above (or below) the average that would be obtained if the student had used the same optimal C level for all of their answers as shown in *Figure 1*. Negative bonuses are common in self-tests when students often have misconceptions (confident errors), but students should aspire to gaining positive bonuses of 2-5%.

2 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PRACTICE EXAM

In order to take a snapshot of the students' knowledge and provide them with this feedback, they were required to complete an online practice exam worth 5% of the total subject assessment in the final week of semester. The format of the practice exam closely resembled the actual end of semester exam, which is comprised of 40 one correct answer MCQs (40%) and several short answer questions (60%). Completing past exam papers is a relatively common observed method of study for students, however most tend not to complete them under strict exam conditions, for example in study groups. Furthermore, as a matter of policy the School of Engineering does not provide solutions to past exam papers which may shape students' study habits with past exams. Students were encouraged to complete the practice exam under realistic exam-like conditions and would receive direct feedback, obviating the need to provide solutions to past exams. In addition, becoming accustomed to the format, length and difficulty of past exam papers acts as a means for students preparing themselves for the final exam. The added benefit is that taking a test generally improves students' performance on a later test; this is referred to as the "testing effect" (Kuo & Hirshman, 1996).

The online practice exam comprised of 40 multiple choice questions utilising CBM, worth 5% of the final subject assessment. The format of the practice exam was chosen to closely resemble the format of the multiple-choice section of the final exam, in terms of both content and number of questions. This similarity would ensure that students were provided with an accurate instrument to assess their knowledge and indicate their potential final exam performance. Some questions were parameterised to dissuade students from sharing answers. Students could review their answers before submitting their exam to be electronically graded.

The practice exam was administered in the final week of semester. In 2015 and 2016, students were to complete the exam within the week with no time limit, whereas in 2017 students were limited to a total time of 90 minutes. This decision was made in order to ensure that the students were completing the practice exam under exam-like

conditions and not treating it as further continuous assessment such as an assignment, where the goal is to try to maximise one's mark rather than assess one's knowledge. Feedback was provided to the students immediately upon the exam closing at the end of the week and was provided for each question in the form of their selected confidence level, their selected answer and the correct answer. Summary feedback was provided in the form of their accuracy score (raw percentage of questions correct), CBM average score and a bonus-adjusted accuracy score.

3 RESULTS

Students who did not complete all 40 questions on the online practice exam were excluded from the following analyses. Repeating students only had their first attempt counted when comparing across years.

3.1 Overall practice exam performance

Figure 2 shows the performance of the 2304 students that fully completed the online practice exam over the three semesters it has been running. The dashed line indicates the maximum possible CBM score for a given accuracy level (percentage correct), which would be obtained if students (unrealistically) selected high confidence for every correct question and low confidence for every incorrect question. The solid line indicates the average CBM score that would be obtained if the student had used the same optimal confidence level for all of their answers. Accuracy scores would receive a bonus proportional to the amount the average CBM mark is above (or below) this line. It is clear that most of the CBM scores are above this line, although there are several extreme outliers.

Figure 2. Online practice exam results 2015-2017 (N=2304)

Figure 3 shows the CBM adjusted accuracy score, where most students received a positive bonus (point lies above the dashed line), indicating that to a large degree their confidence levels reflected their accuracy.

Figure 3. Online practice exam CBM adjusted accuracy (N=2304)

Table 1 shows the mean and variance values for the accuracy (percentage correct reported as a decimal number) and CBM average scores across the three semesters. It appears as though there is a significant decrease in both of these quantities from 2016 to 2017. In particular, performing Levene's test for equality of variances indicates a statistically significant difference in variances for both the accuracy ($F = 11.521, p < 0.001$) and the CBM average ($F = 6.254, p < 0.012$) from 2016 to 2017. Moreover, conducting a series of independent samples t-tests on the different years' results (accuracy and CBM average) reveals no statistically significant difference between 2015 and 2016, but a statistically significant difference in both the accuracy ($t = -7.456, p < 0.0001$) and the CBM average ($t = -6.830, p < 0.0001$) from 2016 to 2017. It could therefore be reasonably surmised that the imposition of a time limit on the practice exam in 2017 has caused both of these values to decrease.

Table 1. Results for students across the three semesters

	Year					
	2015 (N=751)		2016 (N=851)		2017 (N=702)	
	Mean	Var	Mean	Var	Mean	Var
Accuracy	0.8162	0.0136	0.8277	0.0140	0.7802*	0.0169
CBM Average	1.7407	0.4125	1.7993	0.3904	1.5707*	0.4644

* indicates a statistically significant difference to 2015 and 2016

3.2 Practice exam performance for subgroups

The results for the average CBM score and accuracy were split according to the gender of the students and are given in Table 2. Female students performed slightly better than males in terms of the mean of both the average CBM score and the accuracy score. Levene's test for the equality of variances for the accuracy score ($F = 1.955, p = 0.162$) and for the CBM score ($F = 1.381, p = 0.240$), showed no meaningful difference in variances across the two groups. A subsequent t-test for the equality of both means assuming equal variances indicated that the observed difference in means was not statistically significant, to a standard significance level of 0.05.

Table 2. Results for male (N=1759) and female (N=545) students

	Accuracy		Average CBM score	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Mean	0.8074	0.8162	1.6990	1.7481
Variance	0.0147*	0.0166*	0.4181*	0.4627*

* indicates a statistically significant difference across groups

Table 3 looks at the breakdown of results according to gender over the three years in detail to see if there was any difference in the effect of imposing a time limit in 2017. Indeed, there was a statistically significant difference in the means of both the accuracy ($t=2.307$, $p < 0.021$) and CBM average ($t=2.380$, $p < 0.018$) between male and female students, but only for the 2017 iteration of the practice exam which was lower than both 2015 and 2016. The imposition of the time limit may have accounted for these decreases.

Table 3. Results for students across the three semesters according to gender

		Year					
		2015		2016		2017	
		F (N=157)	M (N=594)	F (N=206)	M (N=645)	F (N=182)	M (N=520)
Accuracy	Mean	0.8025	0.8198	0.8416	0.8232	0.7993*	0.7736*
	Var	0.0180	0.0124	0.0131	0.0142	0.0182	0.0163
CBM Average	Mean	1.6654	1.7605	1.8767	1.7746	1.6738*	1.5346*
	Var	0.5357	0.3791	0.3804	0.3916	0.4678	0.4590

* indicates statistical significance between groups within that year

Table 4 presents the selected confidence levels and percent correct at each confidence level according to gender (male / female). The high confidence level was selected by the majority of students in both subgroups, with slightly more male students choosing it than females. However, female students got slightly more questions correct at this level, which could perhaps explain the overall differences in accuracy and CBM average noted in Table 3. Interestingly, the percentages correct at each confidence level are all within a few percent for the both subgroups, indicating relatively similar judgement skills in terms of assessing confidence levels and within the suggested percentage bounds explained in Section 1.

Table 4. Confidence levels for male (N=1759) and female (N=545) students

Confidence Level	Gender		Percent Correct	Gender	
	Male	Female		Male	Female
Low	16%	15%	Low	46%	47%
Medium	15%	18%	Medium	71%	74%
High	69%	67%	High	91%	92%

3.3 Final exam performance

The final exam performance of students was correlated with various other assessment tasks including assignments, in-class activities and both the practice exam accuracy and practice exam average CBM score as shown in Table 5. It is apparent that the

average CBM score is the strongest predictor of final exam performance, more so than the practice exam accuracy score.

Table 5. Correlation (Pearson) of subject assessments with final exam performance (N = 2289)

Assessment Item	Correlation with final exam score
In-class activities	0.430*
Assignments	0.443*
Practice exam accuracy	0.464*
Practice exam average CBM score	0.490*

* indicates correlation is significant at the $p = 0.01$ level

4 DISCUSSION

The online practice exam, utilising CBM, has shown to be an effective assessment and feedback mechanism for students and educators alike. From the overall bonuses calculated and the distribution of percent correct at each confidence level in *Table 4*, most students took judging their confidence seriously, although some appeared to either not understand the importance of the confidence measure or tried to “game” the system as seen in some of the outliers in *Figure 2*.

While female students have outperformed male students over the three years as a whole, the effect is not statistically significant. As would reasonably be expected, the imposition of a time limit for completing the practice exam, in order to more closely resemble the final exam, negatively affected overall results. This is likely due to students not having enough time to revise and check their answers. Under the conditions of the time limit it was observed that there was a statistically significant difference in the performance between males and females; whether this is an ongoing characteristic of the assessment or simply a one-semester result will have to be seen in subsequent years.

Further study is required to determine how the practice exam feedback, in particular the confidence levels, is utilised by the students for study purposes.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper presented the implementation of an online practice exam, utilising CBM, in a large first-year engineering subject and a dissemination of student results over its three years of operation. The CBM approach adds little complexity but offers students and educators much more meaningful feedback than a simple multiple-choice quiz. Students can use their results and confidence indicators to identify potential misconceptions and inform their study leading up to the final exam. Educators can use aggregated data in order to identify misconceptions common across the cohort. In particular, the CBM average score is the strongest predictor of final exam performance, with a stronger correlation than the simple accuracy score alone. Further investigation of the results for different subgroups and surveying of students may lead to more insights into the effects of its implementation.

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